

An Edible Polyomavirus Vaccine

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Abstract

In this study, we investigate the hypothesis that food-grade vaccine antigens might be immunogenic when delivered via non-injection routes. Brewer's yeast were engineered to express the VP1 major capsid protein of BK polyomavirus (BKV), as a model vaccine antigen. In support of conventional wisdom, purified VP1 or crude lysates of VP1-expressing yeast were not immunogenic when delivered to mice orally. Surprisingly, simply feeding mice live VP1-expressing yeast mixed with mouse chow induced robust antibody responses. In contrast to oral delivery, mice administered yeast lysates intranasally or intradermally mounted strong antibody responses to purified VP1. The neutralizing antibody titers of an author who home-brewed and drank live BKV VLP yeast increased from undetectable to moderate. The implications of these findings are revolutionary. Food-based vaccines are dramatically faster, easier, and cheaper to produce and are less painful than traditional injection vaccines. For some populations, edible vaccines may also be more acceptable and accessible than existing pharmaceutical products.

Introduction

BK polyomavirus (BKV) and its close relative JC polyomavirus (JCV) cause kidney, bladder, brain, and cardiovascular diseases (Lee et al., 2019; Petrogiannis-Haliotis et al., 2001; Pinto & Dobson, 2014; Robles et al., 2020; Sandler et al., 1997; Starrett et al., 2023). For the past fifteen years, our group has pursued the development of an intramuscular BKV/JCV vaccine that could protect against these diseases.

Although the production of highly immunogenic virus-like particles (VLPs) representing BKV is straightforward at laboratory scale, generation of larger amounts of highly purified material suitable for adjuvanted injection into human subjects has been expensive and time-consuming. In this report, we test the hypothesis that food-grade BKV VLP preparations might be immunogenic when delivered via non-injection routes.

Early vaccines consisted of crude preparations of attenuated pathogens delivered via oral, nasal, or dermal routes (Gupta et al., 2025). Although there has been preclinical progress toward the development of edible recombinant vaccines (Austriaco, 2023; Kumar et al., 2025), a large majority of modern vaccines use killed pathogens or purified subunits that are injected intramuscularly or subcutaneously.

There has long been a general rule of thumb suggesting oral vaccine delivery can only work using replication-competent microbes, but some noteworthy exceptions have emerged. For example, a recently developed cholera vaccine that uses orally delivered killed bacteria and a recombinant toxin subunit is highly effective (Khanam et al., 2025). The oral cholera vaccine conforms to the classic observation that proteins capable of binding certain glycans are more orally immunogenic than other soluble antigens, perhaps due to their ability to associate with intestinal microfold (M) cells that pass antigens from the gut lumen to underlying lymphoid structures (de Aizpurua & Russell-Jones, 1988). BKV virions bind a variety of cell-surface glycans, including some that are chemically similar to the ganglioside headgroups targeted by cholera toxin (Geoghegan et al., 2017; Pastrana et al., 2013).

Recent clinical trials using BKV-neutralizing monoclonal antibodies have confirmed the idea that humoral immunity can reduce the risk of post-transplant nephropathy [NCT05769582](#) [NCT04294472](#) (Costa et al., 2025; Jordan et al., 2022). The remarkable success of HPV vaccines confirms a model originally proposed by Bachmann and colleagues in which antigens with rigid repetitive spacing in the 50-100Å range can elicit strong and highly durable B cell responses (Bachmann et al., 1993; Buck, 2023; Schiller & Lowy, 2015). Polyomaviruses, like HPVs, are non-enveloped viruses whose icosahedral capsids are built from self-assembling structural proteins that naturally display rigidly repetitive spacing. We have previously shown that

polyomavirus VLP vaccines elicit remarkably potent and long-lasting neutralizing antibody responses in animal model systems (Lučiūnaitė et al., 2023; Peretti et al., 2023).

In this study, we find that robust serological responses can be achieved using unpurified BKV VLP vaccine immunogens. The results open the door to the production and rapid testing of inexpensive vaccines that can immediately be delivered in the form of ordinary commercial food products.

Methods

Plasmid construction and yeast transformation. IDT's codon modification [tool](#) was used to adapt VP1 sequences for expression in brewer's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*). The initial codon modified sequence outputs were polished to remove sequences resembling yeast splicing signals (Iwata & Gotoh, 2011). The BKV genotype IVc2 VP1 used for this study is based on strain A-66H (GenBank accession BAG84476). Codon modified ORFs were synthesized as gBlocks HiFi gene fragments (IDT). The VP1 ORF was cloned into the yeast expression vector pFx7m using *XbaI* and *XmaI* restriction enzymes (NEB). The pFx7m plasmid is a derivative of pFX7 (Sasnauskas et al., 1999) that was modified to contain a zeocin resistance gene for bacterial selection and a multi-cloning site. The pFx7m plasmid retains the original *Candida maltosa* formaldehyde dehydrogenase (FDH1) gene for selection of stably transformed yeast using formaldehyde-containing medium.

Maltose-inducible expression plasmids were assembled entirely from synthetic DNA fragments (GeneUniversal) using standard restriction enzyme-based cloning methods (NEB). The *C. maltosa* FDH1 cDNA was codon modified to conform to *S. cerevisiae* codon usage (IDT). Promoters, introns, ribosome binding sites, and polyadenylation signals were chosen based on the following references: (Cuperus et al., 2017; Curran et al., 2013; Hoshida et al., 2017; Ito et al., 2020; Meurer et al., 2017; Niederer et al., 2022; Savinov et al., 2021).

Yeast transformation was carried out using the lithium acetate/polyethylene glycol (LiAc/PEG4000) method with a 25 minute heat shock at 42°C (Ito et al., 1983) or with a Frozen-EZ Yeast Transformation II Kit (Zymo Research) according to manufacturer instructions. Cells were allowed to recover overnight in YPD medium at 30 °C without shaking. The following day, cells were pelleted and plated onto YPD-agar containing 4 mM formaldehyde (or other formaldehyde concentrations specified in Table S1) diluted from a 37% stock (ThermoFisher). Plates were incubated at 30°C for 48 hours to allow colony formation. Colonies were streaked onto fresh YPD-agar plates containing 6 mM formaldehyde and incubated at 30 °C for 2 days to select for stably transformed yeast. For pGustiv transformants, colonies were streaked onto Propper malt extract (Omega Yeast) plates and colonies were inspected under blue light through an orange filter.

Yeast Cultivation, Induction, and VLP Expression. A transformed yeast colony was shaken overnight at 30 °C in 25 ml of YPD medium supplemented with 4 mM formaldehyde to serve as a pre-culture. The following day, this pre-culture was transferred to 225 ml of YPD and shaken overnight. The cells were then harvested by centrifugation at 500 x g for 5 minutes, and the resulting pellets were resuspended in 250 ml of YP broth containing 3% galactose (YPG) (BioPure). The cultures were returned to the shaker at 30 °C for 18-22 hours to induce VP1 expression. Yeast with Gusto-series plasmids were induced by transferring the starter culture into 1x Propper malt extract broth overnight (Omega Yeast)(Buck & Buck, 2025).

Yeast cells were collected by centrifugation at 500 x g and the wet biomass pellet was weighed (typically about 12.5 g). A live yeast slurry was generated by suspending the pellet in roughly one volume (approximately 12.5 ml) of YPD media. For lysis, yeast pellets were mixed with roughly one pellet volume of acid-washed 500 µm glass beads (Millipore Sigma) and 2.5 pellet volumes of ice-cold disruption buffer (10 mM Tris pH 7.2, 450 mM NaCl, 1 mM CaCl₂, 250 mM Arginine-HCl, 0.01% Triton X-100). Cells were disrupted by alternating 1 min of vortexing with 1 min on ice, for a total of 20 min. Lysates were clarified by centrifugation at 500 x g for 5 min at 4 °C. Clarified supernatants were loaded onto OptiPrep™ gradients for purification of virus-like particles VLPs. Purified baculovirus-produced VLPs were left over from a previous study (Peretti et al., 2023).

Saccharomyces cerevisiae var. *boulardii* CNCM I-3799 yeast (ATCC) were transformed and induced using the same methods. The induced *boulardii* culture was dried by spreading a yeast slurry onto a silicone mat and drying it at ambient temperature in room air under an Airmega Aim fan (Coway). The resulting chips of dried yeast were either fed directly to mice or mixed with kibble.

SDS-PAGE and Western Blot Analysis. Samples were mixed with LDS sample buffer (Invitrogen), heated, and then loaded onto a 12% SDS-PAGE gel run in MOPS-based NuPAGE buffer. Following electrophoresis, proteins were visualized using Coomassie Brilliant Blue staining (Abcam). For Western blotting, separated proteins were transferred onto an Invitrolon PVDF membrane (Invitrogen). Membranes were blocked overnight at 4°C with gentle agitation in 3% non-fat dry milk prepared in TBS-T (Tris-buffered saline, 0.1% Tween-20). After blocking, membranes were incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature with primary antibody (Pab597, mouse monoclonal antibody reactive against BK, JC, and SV40 VP1 protein, was a kind gift from Walter Atwood) diluted 1:3000 in blocking buffer (final concentration 1.7 µg/ml). Following three washes with TBS-T, membranes were incubated with donkey anti-mouse IgG (H+L) HRP conjugated secondary antibody (BioRad), diluted 1:10,000 in blocking buffer, for 30 minutes at room temperature. After an additional three TBS-T washes, protein bands were detected by chemiluminescence using WesternBright ECL Spray (Advansta) applied for 2 minutes at room temperature. Blots were wrapped in plastic and imaged using a CCD-based detection system.

Western blot-based semi-quantitation indicated that live yeast suspensions and clarified crude lysates typically contained about 0.22 µg/µl of VP1.

Animal Experiments and Immunization Procedures. All animal experiments were conducted following protocols approved by the National Cancer Institute (NCI) Animal Care and Use

Committee. Mice were maintained according to the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals, 8th Edition (2011), published by the National Research Council. Before vaccination, individual animals were identified by toe tattooing. Groups of five six-week-old female BALB/c mice (Jackson Laboratory) were assigned to different immunization regimens as described below. All mice received a booster immunization eight weeks after the priming dose. Blood samples were collected from the mandibular vein at two and seven weeks post-prime immunization, and two weeks after the boost dose (i.e., week 10 in the figure legends) for serological analysis. In preliminary experiments, neutralizing titers assessed seven weeks after the booster dose were comparable to titers observed two weeks after the booster dose (data not shown). The seven-week post-boost datapoint was therefore omitted from subsequent experiments. At the end of the study, euthanasia was carried out by CO₂ inhalation according to approved institutional protocols.

Mice were housed and immunized in groups of five. For some key experiments, such as food-based administration of live yeast, an entirely independent repeat was conducted. Datapoints for all ten animals are plotted together (Figure 2).

Intramuscular Administration:

- For the purified baculovirus-derived VLP vaccine, mice were immunized in the quadriceps muscle with 2 µg of VLP mixed with 2 µg of alum adjuvant in PBS, for a total volume of 25 µL per mouse. For the purified yeast-derived VLP vaccine, mice were immunized intramuscularly with 2 µg of VLP in PBS, without adjuvant, for a total volume of 25 µL per mouse.

Intranasal Administration

- A micropipette was used to inoculate each mouse with 10 µL of crude lysate or live yeast suspension intranasally without adjuvant. For the purified baculovirus-derived VLP vaccine, 2 µg VLP and 2 µg bovine lipid extract surfactant (BLES) adjuvant (Kimoto, 2022) was delivered to the nose and lungs in a total volume of 50 µl (Southam et al., 2002).

Intrarectal Administration:

- Mice were anesthetized with isoflurane immediately before immunization. For purified baculovirus-derived VLP vaccines, mice received 2 µg of VLP and 2 µg cholera toxin B subunit (CTB) (Thiam et al., 2015) in PBS, for a final volume of 50 µL per mouse. For live and crude lysate yeast vaccines, 50 µL per mouse was administered intrarectally without adjuvant.

Transdermal Administration

- The fur over the ventrolateral surface of each mouse was shaved using electric clippers and cleaned with an alcohol pad. A 0.5 mm microneedle cosmetic derma-roller (YaFex) was used to gently abrade the skin surface. Mice then received 200 μ L of live or crude yeast-based vaccine without adjuvant. For purified VLP vaccines, produced in yeast or insect cells, 2 μ g of VLPs were mixed with 2 μ g of alum adjuvant in PBS to a total volume of 200 μ L per mouse. After administration of VLPs to the skin, the area was subjected to further derma-roller treatment. Following vaccine administration, the site was covered with a sterile adhesive dressing. The mice typically chewed the dressing off within an hour or two.

Oral (Gavage) Administration

- Mice were orally gavaged with a formulation containing 2 μ g VLP, 2 μ g cholera toxin B subunit (CTB), 50 μ L of 10% sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3) as a buffering agent, and PBS up to a final volume of 150 μ L per mouse.

Sublingual Administration

- Anesthetized mice were immunized with 2 μ g of purified baculovirus-derived VLPs combined with 2 μ g of CTB as an adjuvant, bringing the total volume to 10 μ L per mouse with the addition of PBS.

Oral Food Administration

- A feeding dose was made by mixing 25 ml of live yeast slurry or yeast lysate with 50 g or 25 g of autoclaved NIH31 diet (Inotiv), respectively. 75 g of live yeast–kibble mixture or 50 g of lysate–kibble mixture was added to each cage of five mice. After 20 hours, the remaining food in each cage was weighed to assess consumption. Mice typically ate an average of 8.5 g each, after accounting for an estimated 10% evaporation loss. The remaining food was then supplemented with untreated kibble *ad libidum*.

Neutralization assays and data analysis. Neutralization assays were conducted using BK polyomavirus type IV (BKV-IV) pseudovirions produced in 293TT cells. A detailed protocol is posted on the Lab of Cellular Oncology [website](#). For the single human volunteer (author CBB), neutralizing titers were tested against pseudoviruses representing BKV genotypes I, II and IV. The pseudovirions carried NanoLuc luciferase reporter plasmids (pcsNuc and phsNuc), as [previously described](#) (Geoghegan et al., 2017; Pastrana et al., 2013; Ray et al., 2015).

HEK293TT cells were seeded at 30,000 cells per well in 96-well plates suitable for tissue culture. Pseudoviruses were incubated with serial 5-fold dilutions of mouse serum for 1 hour at 4 °C in untreated polystyrene 96-well plates. The virus-serum mixtures were then added to the pre-seeded cells and incubated for 72 hours. After incubation, 25 μ L of the culture supernatant was transferred to white luminometry plates (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA) for analysis of

secreted NanoLuc activity. Nano-Glo Luciferase Assay reagent (Promega, Madison, WI) was diluted 1:8 in PBS, and 80 μ l was added to each well. Luminescence was measured using a Synergy microplate reader (BioTek, Winooski, VT) set to a gain of 100. The 50% effective concentration (EC_{50}), defined as the reciprocal serum dilution causing 50% neutralization, was determined using Prism software (GraphPad).

Ethics statement. As a private citizen, author CBB independently synthesized the maltose-inducible BKV-IV/GFP expression plasmid, pGustiv, in his home hobby lab. He then home-transformed brewer's yeast with the plasmid and used the transformed yeast to home brew beer, which he drank. The outside activity, which did not use any NCI resources, is detailed in an independent document entitled, "Vaccine Beer: A Personal Healthcare Report" (Buck & Buck, 2025).

Testing of author CBB's donated serum in the current manuscript was conducted as a pilot public health surveillance activity carried out by a public health authority (NCI). The work aims to monitor a new consumer product (vaccine beer). This type of work is explicitly excluded from the Common Rule's specialized definition of the term "research" under [45 CFR § 46.102\(I\)\(2\)](#).

Although the serology experiments are exempt from mandatory IRB review, author CBB voluntarily consulted the NCI IRB. The IRB approved a self-experimentation protocol entitled, "Investigator Self-Collection of Blood Via Finger Prick for use in Hemagglutination Assays."

Author CBB holds the personal view that, under the principle of autonomy, it is unethical for institutions to exert veto authority over self-experiments (Beauchamp & Childress, 1979; Hanley et al., 2019; Sills et al., 2020; Tharrington, 2024). At a statutory level, self-experiments and other individual healthcare-related activities are insufficiently systematic/generalizable to meet the regulatory definition of human subjects research (Buck & Buck, 2025).

In summary, CBB views the work described in this report as exempt from mandatory IRB review in two distinct ways. He also has IRB approval for this type of work.

Results

Immunization of mice using yeast lysates. Mice were inoculated with clarified lysates of yeast expressing BKV VP1 via different routes. A positive control group received an intramuscular injection of purified BKV VP1 VLPs. Serological responses in the positive control group were comparable to past reports (Pastrana et al., 2013; Peretti et al., 2023).

Mice administered a single 10 μ l intranasal dose of yeast lysate (containing about 2 μ g of VLPs) mounted robust BKV-neutralizing antibody responses in four out of five mice (Figure 1). Mice inoculated intranasally three days in a row showed more uniform responses. Administration of yeast lysates using a cosmetic microneedle derma-roller three days in a row elicited a wide range of neutralizing antibody responses. Lysates administered intrarectally or orally (mixed with food) did not induce detectable neutralizing antibody responses. Similar results were observed in pilot experiments in which mice were administered purified BKV VLPs mixed with adjuvants via various routes (Figure S1).

Route	Injection	Nasal	Nasal	Dermal	Rectal	Oral
Dosing days	1	1	3	3	1	1
Antigen prep	purified	lysate	lysate	lysate	lysate	lysate
VLP quantity	1 µg	2 µg	2 µg	40 µg	10 µg	1 mg

Figure 1: BKV-neutralizing serum antibody responses of mice administered lysates of yeast expressing BKV-IV VLPs. Mice were given a priming dose via the indicated route at time zero. A booster dose was administered via the same route at week 8.

Immunization of mice using live yeast. Administration of live yeast expressing BKV VP1 produced surprisingly different results than experiments with yeast lysates. Most notably, simply mixing live BKV VP1-expressing yeast with ordinary mouse chow induced uniformly robust serological responses (Figure 2). In contrast, intranasal administration of live yeast was not detectably immunogenic. A single dermal administration of live yeast induced a serological response in two out of five animals. Repeat experiments involving intradermal dosing several days in a row will be needed to evaluate whether dermal administration of live yeast is a tractable approach.

The BKV-IV VP1 expression plasmid was transformed into probiotic *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. *boulardii* yeast. The rationale for using the probiotic strain is that it might be superior to the lab strain, in terms surviving drying and persisting in the gut. Mice fed live VP1-expressing *boulardii* slurry showed robust serological responses (Figure S2). Mice fed dried live *boulardii* for two days also showed serological responses, but with wider mouse-to-mouse variability. The mice were fed as a group, and it appeared that less dominant members of the group may not have had adequate access to the yeast chips. Future experiments of this type should investigate outcomes for mice housed individually.

Figure 2: BKV-neutralizing serum antibody responses of mice administered live yeast expressing BKV-IV VLPs via different routes. Mice were given a priming dose via the indicated route at time zero. A booster dose was administered via the same route at week 8.

Development of a simplified expression system. The galactose-inducible system used for the mouse studies may have technical drawbacks for broader use as a food-based vaccine. A major drawback is that food-grade galactose is expensive. Furthermore, a number of research studies suggest that consuming high levels of galactose can cause symptoms of accelerated aging in a variety of model animals (Azman & Zakaria, 2019). Another possible drawback is that some yeast strains, such as the *boulardii* strain tested in this study, are unable to utilize galactose as a carbon source (Pais et al., 2020). We therefore explored the possibility of using a maltose-inducible promoter system (Meurer et al., 2017).

Since laboratory *S. cerevisiae* strains are incapable of utilizing maltose as a carbon source, we turned to commercial brewer's yeast strains (Table S1). An initial barrier to transformation was that some yeast strains exhibited high innate resistance to formaldehyde. This was especially true if the culture was allowed to settle out of suspension or if the yeast were plated at high density. We infer that some strains may employ biofilm-like effects to resist formaldehyde. Consistent with this inference, highly flocculent yeast strains generally seemed particularly resistant to formaldehyde.

A set of three plasmids were designed to co-express different marker genes alongside BKV-IV VP1 under control of the bi-directional MAL32 promoter. A “superfold” mutant of enhanced green fluorescent protein (sfGFP) was chosen as a reporter based on results indicating that its overexpression poses less of a burden to yeast than other fluorescent proteins (Aronson et al., 2011; Fujita et al., 2025; Kaishima et al., 2016). Blue and purple chromogenic proteins from edible sea anemones (*Actinia equina* and *Anemonia viridis*, respectively) were also tested (Lukyanov et al., 2000; Shkrob et al., 2005; Zagranichny et al., 2004). Although the chromogenic reporters were readily visualized in maltose-induced yeast cell pellets, it was difficult to see the color of yeast suspended in culture broth (Figure S3). In contrast, GFP-expressing yeast were readily visualized in suspension.

VP1 genes representing the following polyomaviruses are available in the sfGFP (pGusto) background: BKV-Ib2, BKV-II, BKV-IVc2, JCV-2A, HPyV6, and HPyV7. A Gusto-series plasmid encoding the L1 protein of HPV16 is also available.

Self-serology. Neutralization testing of serum collected before and after author CBB's outside consumption of vaccine beer (Buck & Buck, 2025) revealed a significant increase in neutralizing titers against the cognate BKV genotype IV (BKV-IV) pseudovirus (Figure 3). Interestingly, titers against BKV-II increased as well. This is consistent with prior observations showing that immunization with BKV-IV VLPs can generate a limited subset of antibodies capable of cross-neutralizing other BKV genotypes (Pastrana et al., 2012; Peretti et al., 2023). The results show that drinking yeast expressing BKV VLPs can elicit a humoral response in a human subject.

Figure 3: BKV-neutralizing serum antibody responses before and after drinking yeast expressing BKV-IV VLPs. As an outside activity, author CBB independently home brewed and drank beer containing suspended live yeast expressing BKV-IV VP1 (Buck & Buck, 2025). Beer stein icons indicate roughly five-day dosing windows. Cross-neutralization of BKV genotypes I and II was also monitored. EC₅₀ values from a minimum of four independent neutralization experiments were averaged. Error bars represent one standard deviation.

Discussion

Modern vaccine development requires basic scientists to convince industry partners that it will be profitable to invest millions of dollars developing and testing pharmaceutical-grade vaccine material. Consumers cannot try the vaccine during the years in which it is undergoing the clinical testing required for FDA drug approval.

The finding that food-grade yeast are immunogenic when eaten as a foodstuff opens a surprising new path to vaccine development. Oral food-based vaccines can be produced in an ordinary kitchen and can be immediately marketed under the standard regulatory framework governing commercial food products (Buck & Buck, 2025). Like other food and food-supplement products, suppliers can be covered by standard liability insurance. Vaccine yeast products could also be covered under OpenMTA or other types of open source agreements (Kahl et al., 2018).

Although food-grade GMO yeast products meet regulatory standards for Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) status (Buck & Buck, 2025), consumers would be wise to consider the hypothetical risks of eating a new food product that has not yet been widely consumed. On the other hand, consumers could also consider the risks of BKV-induced diseases and decide to eat a vaccine yeast product in hope that it might ultimately be effective for mitigating these diseases.

A traditional concern about edible vaccines has been the concept that oral exposure to soluble antigens in the absence of adjuvants might induce immune tolerance (Austriaco, 2023). At a serological level, tolerance might be reflected by a lack of boosting effects. In this study, robust boosting effects were observed after food-based vaccine administration, both in mice and in the single human volunteer. Results for the human volunteer showed a puzzling lack of boosting effects after the third round of vaccine beer dosing (Figure 3). Although the results of pilot n-of-1 studies are hard to generalize, we entertain the speculative hypothesis that a secreted IgA antibody response might have coated the VLPs in the lumen of the intestine, thus rendering the VLPs unable to associate with intestinal antigen presenting cells. It seems possible that a shorter interval between doses could be more effective. Alternatively, a testable prediction might be that an additional round of boosting via intradermal or intranasal routes might bypass the hypothetical immune exclusion effects. It is also conceivable that a higher antigen dose, which could be achieved by eating a larger amount of live yeast separated from the alcoholic beer, might overwhelm the hypothetical gut IgA-based blocking effects.

It is unclear whether author CBB's vaccine-induced neutralizing antibody levels would protect him against BKV-induced nephropathy in a hypothetical scenario where he receives a kidney transplant. A landmark study from the Fafi-Kremer group suggests that a neutralizing EC₅₀ titer of 10,000 correlates with protection against BKV nephropathy (Solis et al., 2018). However, the "Solis threshold" has some caveats, including the problem that neutralizing antibody levels

might theoretically be a proxy marker for vigorous cell-mediated immunity. Another issue is that strain variation and neutralization-escape mutations may affect protection thresholds (Peretti et al., 2018; Ray et al., 2015). A revolutionary implication of the current study is that more clues could be gathered about this question simply by alerting individuals on organ transplant waitlists that it is now possible to cheaply make or purchase food-grade yeast expressing BKV and JCV VP1. Ordinary medical recordkeeping could then be used to compare polyomavirus disease outcomes in individuals who choose to eat vaccine yeast prior to transplantation to individuals who did not eat vaccine yeast (or to historical baselines).

Another example of the immediate utility of food vaccines might be a common condition called painful bladder syndrome (also known as interstitial cystitis). Although the cause of painful bladder syndrome is not known, a growing body of literature suggests a subset of sufferers shed high levels of BKV or JCV (Larsen et al., 2022; Robles et al., 2020; Van der Aa et al., 2014; Winter et al., 2015). In traditional vaccine development pipelines, it is necessary to first prove that a given pathogen causes a specific disease and then convince investors that a vaccine against the pathogen will be highly effective for mitigating the disease. Food-based vaccines upend this pipeline. It is suddenly possible to envision a scenario in which individuals with painful bladder syndrome could order and/or home brew yeast food products, eat them, and see whether the bladder pain goes away.

It might be possible to improve upon the current yeast-based BKV vaccine by applying past results showing that VLPs can elicit cell-mediated immunity, including CD8+ CTL effectors, against fusion epitopes carried within the VLP (Greenstone et al., 1998). An informative experiment might be to fuse fragments of the BKV early protein known as large T antigen (LT) to the minor capsid protein VP2 (which is spontaneously incorporated into VLPs) (Buck, 2024) (Jandrig et al., 2021). Cell-mediated immunity against the LT fusion epitopes might offer greater protection against BKV-induced disease.

In future studies, it will be important to test hypotheses about the molecular details of why the live BKV yeast vaccine is immunogenic when administered as a food. There is older literature showing that lectin-like antigens tend to be more immunogenic than other soluble proteins (de Aizpurua & Russell-Jones, 1988). This is likely due to enhanced association with M cells, which sample the intestinal lumen and pass sampled antigens down to underlying lymphoid structures for immune presentation. BKV utilizes sialylated glycans as entry receptors, so an initial experiment would be to mutate the sialic acid binding site on the surface of VP1 (Neu et al., 2013) and test whether the mutation affects immunogenicity in a food-based vaccine setting.

Another hypothesis is that the rigidly repetitive Bachmann-class structure of the VLP might be a key element of its immunogenicity in a food delivery setting. This hypothesis could be tested by mutating the C-terminal domain of VP1 that is required for super-assembly of pentamers into

VLPs. Free pentamers, in contrast to assembled VLPs, do not bind cell surface glycosaminoglycan (GAG) receptors (Geoghegan et al., 2017), so a possible drawback to the pentamer experiment is that it cannot test requirements for Bachmann effects separately from the requirements for GAG-binding lectin effects.

The molecular details of how the food-based BKV VLP yeast approach works should help inform efforts to extend food-based vaccine approaches to other pathogens. For example, yeast could be engineered to express the receptor-binding domain of current avian influenza hemagglutinin or SARS-CoV-2 Spike variants. Results deconstructing the BKV success could offer predictions for whether it will be necessary to retain receptor binding pockets to promote association with intestinal M cells, or whether it is necessary to array the RBD on a repetitive scaffold, such as ferritin (Ober Shepherd et al., 2024).

Supplemental Figures

Figure S1: BKV-neutralizing serum antibody responses mice administered BKV-IV VLPs purified from insect cells via different routes. Mice were given a priming dose via the indicated route at time zero. As noted in the Methods section, the respiratory delivery involved a volume of fluid large enough to be inhaled into the lungs. This might account for the higher immunogenicity compared to subsequent experiments delivering small volumes solely to the nasal cavity. A booster dose was administered via the same route at week 8. Some results are plotted as a single datapoint without error bars because the neutralization assay tested pooled serum from all five mice in the group.

Figure S2: BKV-neutralizing serum antibody responses in mice fed live *S. cerevisiae* var. *boulardii* yeast expressing BKV-IV VP1. Mice were given a priming dose via the indicated route at time zero. A booster dose was administered via the same route at week 8.

Figure S3: Maltose-inducible indicator proteins. Wheat ale yeast were transformed with pRembiv (tube on the left in each panel), pRemiv (middle tube), or pGustiv (right tube) and induced overnight in YP broth with 4% maltose. The reporter gene in each plasmid is beadlet anemone (*Actinia equina*) blue chromoprotein aeCP597, snakelocks anemone (*Anemonia sulcata*) purple chromoprotein asFP595, or a superfold variant of enhanced green fluorescent protein from crystal jellyfish (*Aequorea victoria*). Imaging was conducted using a cellphone camera under room light (left panels) or with blue light illumination with an orange filter.

Symbol	Taxon	Strain	Producer, catalog#	Temp	Flocculation	GFP	Form
A	Boul	Sb48	ATCC, MYA-796	30-37	low	+	4
B	Ale	Witty Kitty	Fermentis, BW-20	18-26	low	++	10
C	Ale	Saison	Fermentis, BE-134	18-26	low	++	6
D	Wine	Lalvin	Lallemand, 71B	15-30	very high	+	6
E	Ale	English	White Labs, WLP002	18-20	high	+	4
F	Boul	CNCM I-745	Florastor, Dual Action	30-37	low	+	4
G	Ale	Nottingham	Lallemand, 10108-06-11	10-25	high	-	4
H	Turbo	Heat Turbo	Still Spirits	20-40	low	+	10
I	Wild	Sourdough	Environmental	18-21	low	-	6
J	Lith	Jovaru	Omega, OYL033	21-35	med-low	++	4
K	Kveik	Hothead	Omega, OYL057	20-35	med-high	-	10
L	Lab	214Δpep4	Gedvilaite, a,his4leu2pep4	29-35	low	-	4
M	Ale	Flash	Morebeer, FBKIT1005	18-29	low	-	8
N	Boul	I-3799	NOW, S. boulardii	30-37	low	+	4
O	Kveik	Opshaug	White Labs, WLP518	25-35	med-high	-	8
P	Lith	Pakruojis	White Labs, WLP4047	24-35	low	++	4
R	Kveik	Hornindal	White Labs, WLP521	22-37	med-high	++	8
S	Lith	Simonaitis	White Labs, WLP4046	24-35	high	-	8
T	Boul	CNCM I-3799	Therapro, Lynside	30-37	low	+	4
U	Ale	Pacific	White Labs, WLP041	18-20	high	-	4
V	Kveik	Voss	Lallemand, LalBrew	25-40	very high	-	8
W	Ale	Wheat	Fermentis, WB-06	18-24	low	++	6

X	Ale	English	Fermentis, S-04	12-26	high	-	6
Y	Bread	Fleischmann's	ABF, Active Dry	27-29	high	++	6
Z	Kveik	Hornindal	Omega, OYL-091	20-35	high	-	8

Table S1: transformation properties of brewer's yeast. A maltose-inducible VP1/GFP co-expression plasmid, pGustiv, was transformed into various yeast strains. Abbreviations: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. *boulardii* (Boul), brewer's yeast (Ale), distiller's yeast (Turbo), environmentally derived yeast (Wild), Norwegian farmhouse yeast (Kveik), Lithuanian farmhouse yeast (Lith), baker's yeast (Bread). The GFP column indicates the qualitative brightness of green fluorescence in colonies plated on Propper malt extract agar plates without formaldehyde. The "Form" column indicates the selective dose of formaldehyde (millimolar) used for selecting transformants.

Disclaimer

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Disclosure

Authors DVP and CBB are inventors on polyomavirus vaccine patents. They receive licensing royalties for these inventions.

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